

RESEARCH

KNEE
OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Introduction

Research practice is an integral part of the educational process and is important in the training of a qualified specialist. It is aimed at consolidating and deepening the knowledge and skills acquired by students in the learning process, as well as mastering the system of professional skills.

A brief description of nosology, why are you interested in it.

I choose the nosology of osteoarthritis of the knee because It is a topic that concerns many people, and the knee joint is important for movement in all aspects of life, and it negatively affects patients because it makes a person broken due to difficulty in movement, so interest in this topic makes me more interested in helping people recover from difficulty in movement. Osteoarthritis is a degenerative joint condition. It causes pain, swelling and stiffness, affecting a person's ability to move freely. Osteoarthritis affects the entire joint, including the tissues around it. It is most common in the knees, hips, spine and hands. Many factors can contribute to developing osteoarthritis. Some include a history of joint injury or overuse, older age and being overweight. It affects women more than men.

The purpose of this study the goal of treating osteoarthritis is to ease your pain, help you move better, and stop it from getting worse. Treatment usually begins with: Exercises to improve strength, flexibility and balance. Weight loss, if needed, to improve pain, especially in your hips or knees.

Epidemiology

The prevalence of knee OA varied across studies according to its definition, diagnostic method, and range of age included. Such differences are reflected by the heterogeneity of data reported by studies conducted worldwide.

A recent meta-analysis conducted in China investigated the prevalence of knee OA in symptomatic patients by including 21 studies for an overall number of 74,908 subjects . The overall prevalence of OA was reported to be 14.6% from studies performed in a period ranging from 2012 to 2016. Females presented with a higher knee OA prevalence than males (19.1% vs. 10.9%, respectively). The prevalence also increased with age. A demographic study from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (KNHANES) analyzed the prevalence of radiographic OA from 12,287 subjects older than 50 years and found it to be 35.1% . Again, women were at higher risk of developing knee OA than men. Data from the Chingford Study in the United Kingdom showed that over 5 years the incidence of radiographic knee OA was 17.6% in women with ages ranging from age 45 to 64 years. A study from the United States (US) estimated the incidence of symptomatic knee OA (OA) with the use of self-reported population-based data, reporting that approximately 9.29% of subjects older than 60 years presented a diagnosis of symptomatic knee OA . Moreover, the overall estimated lifetime risk was reported to be 13.83%.

Although OA is not an unavoidable consequence of aging, extensive evidence confirms age as the single major risk factor for the development of OA, especially in weight-bearing joints such as hips and knees . This finding has clearly emerged from several radiographic studies, which showed typical radiographic changes (joint space narrowing and osteophytosis) being very common in the population as the age increases (almost 50% of prevalence in subjects older than 80 years). At the same time, diagnosing symptomatic OA only based on radiographic findings may result in its overestimation, as considerable discordance between joint pain and imaging has been found.

Pathogenesis of OA

At the joint level, many knee structures offer a certain degree of mechanical and functional support to maintain a healthy joint . The subchondral bone (mainly composed of mineralized type I collagen) assists the articular cartilage (mainly constituted of type II collagen and proteoglycans) in providing a surface for joint movement. The menisci provide a significant role in attenuating mechanical forces due to their structure of water, proteoglycans, and collagen. Finally, the synovial fluid to lubricate the articular space is produced by the synovial membrane: it is generally composed of hyaluronic acid and lubricin (also known as proteoglycan 4, PRG4) . Of note, the superficial cartilage layer plays a vital role in constricting water content within the cartilage, acting as a regulator of water content: injuries of early damage to the superficial layer change the water content and, therefore, diminish the load-bearing properties of cartilage .

In the early stages of knee OA, alterations in the structure of collagen and proteoglycans are observed, together with degenerative changes in the meniscal structure. Both of these conditions lead to overcoming the compensatory mechanisms that limit the articular cartilage damage, ultimately, causing meniscal damage and articular cartilage erosions. Of note, the proinflammatory role of cytokines has been confirmed as an essential mechanism of articular damage during the early stages of OA. In response to cartilage erosions, chondrocytes first go through a phase of hypertrophic activity to increase the matrix synthesis, producing inflammatory mediators that propagate cartilage degradation. The ultimate stage of cartilage destruction is chondrocyte apoptosis, leading to an imbalance in the synthesis and catabolism of collagen and proteoglycans in favor of catabolism. Inflammatory mediators spread to other joint structures, causing changes in the synovial tissue and subchondral bone causing bone sclerosis and increasing the thickness of the synovial membrane and capsular structures. Ultimately, gaps are produced in the cartilage surface, with free cartilage fragments propagating the synovial inflammatory condition, a condition that further decreases the synthesis of synovial molecules (lubricin and hyaluronic acid) [40]. The expression of type II collagen (a prominent component of cartilage) decreases during chondrocyte growth; therefore, mature chondrocytes are incapable of producing type II collagen de novo.

Of note, although the changes in the subchondral bone have been traditionally implicated in the OA pathogenesis at a later stage, recent studies identified this joint

structure as one of the first actors in the pathological process. Indeed, recent evidence suggests the existence of specific crosstalk between subchondral bone and articular cartilage. For example, contributing to OA progression has been attributed to altered venous outflow circulation in the subchondral bone, causing physicochemical changes that stimulate osteoblasts to express bone remodeling and cartilage-damaging cytokines . A recent study by Wu et al. investigated the relationship between OA subchondral bone-derived exosomes (membrane-derived vesicles implicated in intercellular communication) and chondrocytes. The study showed that in coculture studies, OA sclerotic subchondral bone osteoblast-derived exosomes were internalized by chondrocytes, causing the expression of catabolic genes, as observed in OA cartilage. Therefore, it seems that such exosomes are crucial in OA progression, representing a possible target for OA treatments . As osteoarthritis is a degenerative disease, the concept of cellular senescence has also been suggested to understand its pathogenesis . Cellular senescence of chondrocytes has been associated with the progressive reduction in cell cycle activity until it eventually stops, apoptosis resistance, and the progressive production of senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP) . Different types of molecules can represent SASPs, yet—in the setting of OA—SASPs are all those inflammatory factors previously described (such as cytokines and chemokines). SASPs can be produced not only by chondrocytes, but also by other cells within the OA joint, such as osteoblasts, synovial fibroblasts, and macrophages . For example, TGF- β and IL-6 are both SASP factors that can contribute to chondrocyte aging by activating p15, p21, and p27, therefore, promoting its senescence through the SMAD complex or STAT3 pathway . Additionally, the release of SASPs by senescent chondrocytes can produce a chemotactic effect on surrounding immune cells; thus, establishing an inflammatory environment further stimulates cartilage degradation .

Etiology of OA

OA has a multifactorial etiologies, which occurs due to interplay between systemic and local factors. Osteoarthritis affects all ages. The etiology of this debilitating disease in which several responsible genes are linked for its occurrence. Sports participation, injury to the joint, obesity, and genetic susceptibility predispose adolescent athletes to the development of premature osteoarthritis. Previous knee trauma increases the risk of knee OA 3.86 times. Old age, female gender, overweight and obesity, knee injury, repetitive use of joints, bone density, muscle weakness, and joint laxity all play roles in the development of joint OA Determination of risk factors particularly in the weight-bearing joints and their modification may reduce the risk of OA and prevent subsequent pain and disability. Mechanical forces exerted on the joints are a significant cause of OA and one of the most modifiable risk factors as determined by body BMI. Female sex, lower educational levels, obesity, and poor muscular strength are associated with symptomatic disease and subsequent disability .

In a review of literature 14 contributing variables including occupational (extrinsic) and personal (intrinsic) were considered as risk factors. Two factors of kneeling and squatting are considered the main primary risk factors in correlation with knee disorders .

Frequent squatting predispose people to development of knee OA. Approximately 40% of men and approximately 68% of women reported squatting ≥ 1 hour per day at age 25. Prolonged squatting is a strong risk factor for tibiofemoral knee OA among elderly. Occupation involving squatting or kneeling more than two hours daily were associated with two-fold significantly increased risk of moderate to severe radiographic knee OA. Obesity alone or in patients with metabolic syndrome increases the risk of radiographic knee OA but has a lesser effect progression of knee OA. Relationship between BMI and OA of the knee is mainly linear, and duration of increased joint loading or gaining weight is also significant. Twenty seven percent of cases of hip arthroplasty and 69% knee arthroplasty may be attributed to obesity (1). In a systematic literature search obesity was consistently the main factors with knee OA by OR=2.63 .

Obesity is also associated with the hip and hand OA. This indicates that excess adipose tissue produces humoral factors, altering articular cartilage metabolism. It has been postulated that the leptin system could be a link between metabolic abnormalities in obesity and increased risk of OA. Meniscal surgery increases the risk of future knee OA by 2.6 times. Patients undergoing partial meniscectomy and reconstruction surgery are significantly more likely to develop radiographic evidence of osteoarthritis than those with normal menisci . Inflammatory process has been shown to be associated with OA. Inflammation may have a contributive role in the development and progression of OA. In one study the median level of high sensitive CRP in progressive knee OA was higher than non-progressive disease . The median value of CRP is significantly associated with functional disability, joint tenderness, pain, fatigue, global severity, and depression in OA. Mean CRP level in OA is greater than healthy individuals .

In a study of relationship between biochemical markers of arthritis and the radiographic grading of osteoarthritis (OA) in knees, a significant relationship was found between the joint space width and radiographic knee OA. The joint space width decreased with increasing Kellgren-Lawrence grade.

Pyridinoline and TIMP-1 exhibited a significant relationship to the Kellgren-Lawrence grade but only urinary pyridinoline had a significant correlation . In another study, raised serum CRP at entry was predictor of knee OA progression. Serum CRP at entry was not predictive of progression between entry and five years but serum CRP at -3 years was predictive of progression by OR=1.95 . Female sex was a strong risk factor even in the subgroup without radiographic knee OA (KL=0/1) For instance, the greater total body fat of the average adult female may partially account for the gender disparity toward OA, given that females theoretically demonstrate higher levels of adipose derived systemic leptin concentrations than their male counterparts.. Female gender increases the risk of knee OA 1.84 times . In patients with knee OA particularly at early stage of the levels of serum vitamin D is significantly lower than individuals without knee OA. Vitamin D deficiency increases the risk of knee OA by OR=2.63. Higher than 6 pregnancies increases the risk of knee OA by 1.95 times .

Table 1.

Risk factors of knee osteoarthritis

Age
Genetic susceptibility
Obesity
Female gender
Trauma
Repetitive knee trauma
Muscle weakness
Joint laxity
Mechanical forces
Kneeling
Squatting
Miniscal injuries

Clinical picture of OA

Persist knee pain, limited morning stiffness, and reduced function are the three symptoms that are recommended for the diagnosis of knee OA by the EULAR. In addition crepitus, restriction of joint movement and bony enlargement are also very useful for diagnosis of knee OA.

Pain is the most common symptom in knee OA, a leading cause of chronic disability, and a major source of the disability attributable to OA. Pain severity ranging from barely perceptible to immobilizing. Pain, in knee OA typically exacerbates by activity and relieves by rest. In the presence of the above six symptoms and signs the probability of having radiographic knee OA increases to 99%.

In advanced cases synovitis may appear and leads to pain at rest or night. Short duration of stiffness less than 30 minutes may be seen in OA patients in the morning or following periods of inactivity.

Tenderness to palpation of involved joints may be evident in physical examination. Joint effusions may be present, which typically exhibit a mild pleocytosis, normal viscosity, and modestly elevated protein. Crepitus during joint motion or walking is a common. Limitation of range of motion are all common signs of OA of the knee. In advanced cases malalignment may be apparent (genu varus or genu valgus).

Diagnosis

Early recognition of patients with knee OA and correction of risk factors is important. Diagnosis can be made based on history and clinical features. However, in a number of patients especially in patients with suspected clinical features, confirmation of OA or determining the extent of joint involvement may require performance of radiography or MRI examinations. Information with regard to some clinical features and risk factors such as age, sex, body mass index, absence of whole leg pain, traumatic onset, difficulties in descending the stairs, palpable effusion, fixed-flexion deformity, restricted-flexion range of motion, and crepitus are helpful and predict the development of radiographic findings in favor of knee OA with a sensitivity and a specificity of 94% and 93%, respectively. Diagnosis of knee may also be possible according to the American College of Rheumatology criteria ([table 1](#)), as well as by using EULAR diagnostic criteria. Based on the latter criteria the presence of 3 symptoms (persistent knee pain, limited morning stiffness and reduce function), and 3 signs (crepitus, restricted movement and bony enlargement) can correctly diagnose 99% of knee OA when all 6 symptoms and signs are present.

Table 1.

American College of Rheumatology criteria for the diagnosis of knee osteoarthritis

Using history and clinical examination*

Pain in the knee and three of the following

- 1-Age >50 years
- 2- Morning stiffness <30 minutes
- 3-Crepitus on active motions
- 4-Bony tenderness
- 5-Bony enlargement
- 6-No palpable warmth of synovium

Using history and clinical examination and radiographic findings

Pain in the knee and one of the following

- 1-Age >50 years
- 2- Morning stiffness < 30 minutes
- 3-Crepitus on active motions and osteophyte

Using history and clinical examination and laboratory findings

Pain in the knee and 5 of the following

- 1- Age >50 years
 - 2- Morning stiffness <30 minutes
 - 3-Crepitus on active motions
 - 4-Bony enlargement
 - 5-No palpable warmth of synovium
 - 6-ESR <40 mm/h
 - 7-Rheumatoid Factor <1/40
 - 8-Synovial fluid signs of osteoarthritis
-

Differential Diagnosis

Several conditions should be considered in the differential diagnosis of knee OA. Septic arthritis, inflammatory articular diseases can be ruled out by the pattern of joint involvement and appropriate clinical features and laboratory tests. Bilateral symmetrical small joint pain, swelling and stiffness should arouse the suspicion of RA. The wrist and the knee are commonly affected by pseudogout and the first metatarsophalangeal joint or knee joint involvement may be seen in patients with gout. Stiffness in the shoulder and hip girdles exacerbated in the morning is suggestive of polymyalgia rheumatica. When a definitive diagnosis of knee OA has been made, further investigations in regard to laboratory test are not required.

However, in suspected cases tests such as CBC, ESR and CRP, uric acid may provide further diagnostic facilities and performance of x-rays for the affected joints especially following trauma, may be helpful for definitive diagnosis. Pes anserinus tendinitis/bursitis is a frequent cause of knee pain in patients with knee OA which should be considered in patients with localized periarticular symptoms or signs. Valgus deformity increases the possibility of this condition by 5.2 times and collateral instability increases the development of tendinitis/bursitis by 6 times .

Treatment

There is no cure for the treatment of OA and most treatments aimed to manage pain and movement restriction. Optimal management of patients with knee OA requires a combination of nonpharmacological and pharmacological modalities of therapy. Based on the available data, there is no statistically significant difference between nonpharmacological and pharmacological therapies.

The initial aim of treatment is often focused on alleviating the pain. Acetaminophen and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are often employed for the relief of mild to moderate pain. However, NSAIDs are typically more effective than acetaminophen but due to higher complications of long term NSAIDS therapy, acetaminophen should be considered the first-line of therapy. In the absence of an adequate response or in case of more severe OA and presence of inflammation, alternative therapy should be considered. Long-term efficacy and safety of acetaminophen have been questioned recently. Combination of NSAIDS and acetaminophen may be used in conditions which neither of them alone are not sufficient for controlling pain or it is required to reduce NSAIDs dosages. COX-2 inhibitors are considered for patients who are at risk of gastrointestinal bleeding. However, these drugs are associated with increased risk of cardiovascular complications .

Acetaminophen is better yet to be taken regularly every day rather than as required, whereas, NSAIDs should be given at the lowest effective dosage for the shortest period of time. NSAIDs are superior to acetaminophen based on meta analysis of randomized clinical trials. The clinical response rate to NSAIDs as well as the proportion of patients who prefer taking NSAIDs was considerably greater than acetaminophen. However, NSAIDs are associated with more adverse effects than acetaminophen.

Topical NSAIDs provide efficacy similar to oral NSAIDs, but with far less systemic side effects. Cardiovascular, renal, and other serious adverse effects have not been reported by topical NSAIDs. Clinical trial data for these products have demonstrated efficacy superior to placebo or similar to oral diclofenac. Capsaicin cream derived from pepper plants is effective in managing pain and can exert further benefits as adjunctive and alternative to oral analgesic /anti-inflammatory agents. It is required to be regularly applied each day.

Table 2.

Nonpharmacological and pharmacological treatment recommended by the American College of Rheumatology for patients with osteoarthritis

- 1-Patients education
- 2-Weight reduction
- 3-Aerobic exercise
- 4-Physical therapy
- 5-Range-of -motion exercise
- 6-Muscle strengthening exercise
- 7- Assisted device for ambulation
- 8- Patellar tapping
- 9- Appropriate foot wear
- 10- Bracing
- 11- Occupational therapy
- 12- Joint protection and energy conservation.
- 13- Assisted devices for activities of daily living

Activities and Exercise

Patients with knee OA should be encouraged to undertake regular aerobic walking exercise and muscle strengthening exercise and range of motion exercises.

This may provide moderate improvement for both pain and quadriceps muscle strength. Patients with knee OA similar to healthy subjects can pursue physical activities to a level that does not increase the pain, provided that, the activity is not painful and does not predispose them to further trauma, higher levels of physical activities may also be permitted.

It should be considered that daily life activities as a risk factor for knee OA may increase the intensity and duration of pain. Nevertheless, engaging in regular recreational activities may be permitted for as long as they do not increase joint pain. In sedentary knee OA exercises and other structured activities have shown to exert favorable effect on pain.

Walking aids can reduce pain in patients with knee OA. Optimal use of a cane or crutch in the contralateral hand are being used in about 40% of patients with knee or hip OA.

Physical therapy

Patients with symptomatic knee OA may benefit with physical therapy. Patients should be instructed appropriate exercise to reduce pain and improve functional capacity. In one study, physical therapy improved pain, physical function and WOMAC indices for short term period and even extended up to one year in a number of patients .However, in some studies, there was no difference in benefit compared with standard therapy.

Using thermal modalities may be effective for relieving symptoms of knee OA. Cryotherapy may be administered by the application of ice packs or massage with ice. On the other hand, short term diathermy was not effective.

Surgery

Knee OA should be initially treated conservatively, and surgery should be considered if knee symptoms have not been controlled despite adequate nonpharmacological and pharmacological therapy.

Surgical treatments for knee OA include arthroscopy, osteotomy and knee arthroplasty. Determining which of these procedures are most appropriate will depend on several factors, including the location and severity of OA damage, patient characteristics and risk factors.

The goal of osteotomy for unicompartmental knee OA is to transfer the weight load from the damaged compartment to undamaged areas, delaying the need for joint replacement. This procedure should be considered in young and active patients who are not suitable candidates for knee arthroplasty. In selected patients with isolated

medial or patellofemoral OA, unicompartmental knee arthroplasty and patellofemoral replacement, respectively, can be successful. Total knee arthroplasty relieves pain and improves quality of life for persons with advanced knee osteoarthritis. For patients with severe OA, total knee arthroplasty can be a safe, rewarding and cost-effective treatment.

Conclusion

knee OA is a frequent condition which predominately involves elderly population. Recognizing the risk factors and correction of associated factors of progression such as obesity, malalignment, vitamin D deficiency, and muscle weakness should be regarded as well. Regarding to irreversibility of OA damages and partial efficacy of available therapy, initiation of any treatment particularly medical treatment should be considered with caution. Because most patients with knee OA are also affected with cardiovascular or renal underlying diseases which may be aggravated with OA medications.

Prevention and control

Several key prevention strategies have been proposed to prevent osteoarthritis and control the disease progression. In particular, reducing overuse of joints (e.g. related to workload), and promoting healthy lifestyles (e.g. regular physical activity, maintaining a normal body weight) play an important role.

The Healing Effect of Bone Marrow-Derived Stem Cells in Knee Osteoarthritis: A Case Report

The patient was a 47 years old nomad female with confirmed magnetic resonance images (MRI) severe right knee OA (classified as stage IV according to the Kellgren and Lawrence classification) . Her BMI was 25 kg/m². She did not respond to corticosteroids, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and glucosamine, chondroitin sulphate or omega3 fatty acids, while she was asked to stop her medications one month prior and also after enrolling for cell transplantation.

Fig. 1

MR images through the right knee joint before stem cell therapy. Proton density (a,b) and T1W gradient echo.

The patient did not have any infection with hepatitis B, C, or HIV, any malignancy, any previous history of allergic reaction to any component of our therapeutic measure, any active cardiac, respiratory, neurologic or endocrine disease necessitating receipt of medication and was not pregnant or in lactating condition. An approval from the Ethics Committee of Shiraz University of Medical Sciences and informed written consent was provided from the patient.

The patient was admitted in Chamran Hospital for physical exam and evaluation of the Western Ontario and McMaster Universities (WOMAC) Osteoarthritis Index, the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) scoring of the pain intensity, walking ability (distance), the number of stairs to climb for the pain to appear, the time till the appearance of gelling, the knee flexion, and the patellar crepitus before and after cell transplantation. Before and after cell transplantation, MRI was undertaken for the affected knee in Faghihi Hospital. MRI of the affected knee was provided preoperatively, 3, 6 and 12 months after treatment on a Seimens 1.5 T MR system in the sagittal, coronal and axial planes.

For bone marrow aspiration, the patient was admitted in Nemazee Hospital. She was placed in prone position and was locally anesthetized with 1% lidocaine and about 60 ml of bone marrow was provided from iliac crest. Cell isolation was undertaken in the clean room of Mother and Child Hospital. Fifty milliliter of phosphate buffer saline (PBS, Clinimax, Germany) was added to the sample, loaded onto a lymphodex (Inno-Train, Germany) and was centrifuged at 1500 g for 20 minutes to collect mononuclear cells. PBS was used to wash the mononuclear cells and they were plated into 150-cm² culture flasks containing 15 ml of alpha modified eagle medium (alpha MEM, Gibco, Germany) supplemented with 10% hyclon serum (Thermo Scientific, USA) and 100 IU penicillin and 100 IU streptomycin (Gibco, Germany).

A sample was provided to test for presence of any possible microbial contamination. Cell expansion was taken place by subcultures and passaged-2 cells were provided for cell injection. Four weeks after plating of cells and in passage-2, they were washed

with PBS and trypsinized with 0.2% trypsin/EDTA and cell counting was performed using a nucleocounter (Chemometec, USA). A total of 36×10^6 cells were provided and under a controlled condition, they were transferred in 2 ml of the media to the operating room for cell transplantation into the knee joint.

Again a sample was provided to check any microbial contamination before injection into the knee. The adhered cells to the flasks were evaluated morphologically under inverted microscopy. Expression of surface markers in the patient's BM-MSCs was evaluated by flow cytometry to evaluate the positive surface biomarkers expression of CD44 and CD90 and absence of CD34 expression.

Cell morphology revealed fibroblastic like adherent cells in all culture flasks ([Figure 2](#)). No contamination was visible in the cell transplantation sample. Flow cytometric findings denoted to expression of CD44 and expression of CD90 (mesenchymal stem cell markers) and negative expression for CD34 (hematopoietic cell marker) ([Figure 3](#)). During the follow-up, no local or systemic adverse events were observed and the patient was satisfied with the therapy after two months with an increasing trend by passing time.

Fig. 2

Emerging of adherent cells with fibroblastic morphology 3 days after culture initiation of the patient's BM-MSCs (P0=primary culture and P1=first passage)

Fig. 3

Expression of surface markers in patient's BM-MSCs. There were positive surface biomarkers expression of CD44 and CD90 and lack of CD34 expression.

Twelve months after cell transplantation, the WOMAC changed from 3 to 2, and the VAS from 80 mm to 11 mm. This modification for walking ability was 170 m before and 700 m after treatment and for the number of stairs to climb for the pain to appear was 5 stairs before and 50 stairs after therapy. The time till the appearance of gelling was 8 min and reached to 30 min and the knee flexion was 100° and improved to 120° twelve months after cell transplantation. The patellar crepitus was 3 before and 2 after therapy. After 6 months, the MRI of the right knee revealed an increase in thickness of the covering cartilage in distal condyle of the femur and the proximal part of the tibia (Figure 4A-C). These changes were much more significant after 12 months follow up (Figure 4D-F).

MR images through the right knee joint six months after stem cell therapy. Proton density (A&C) and T1W gradient echo (B) sections revealed thickness of covering cartilage in distal condyle of femur and proximal part of tibia. MR images through the

right knee joint twelve months after stem cell therapy. Proton density (D&F) and T1W gradient echo (E) sections revealed thickness of covering cartilage in distal condyle of femur and proximal part of tibia.

DISCUSSION

Consistent with our findings, positive therapeutic effects of MSCs in human models were previously shown in different studies. In Jo et al.'s study, patients with knee OA of the knee were transplanted with 1.0×10^7 , 5.0×10^7 and 1.0×10^8 adipose-derived stem cells (AdSCs) into the knee. There was no adverse event and the WOMAC score improved at 6 months after injection and thick, hyaline-like cartilage regeneration was visible. Orozco et al. in patients with knee OA treated with intra-articular injection of 40×10^6 autologous bone marrow-derived stem cells (BM-SCs) observed that the patients demonstrated rapid and progressive improvement of algofunctional indices by 1 year and also showed a highly significant decrease of poor cartilage areas with improvement of cartilage quality.

Injection of BM-SCs in knee OA was shown to improve pain, functional status of the knee, and walking distance without any adverse events. An increase in cartilage thickness and a considerable decrease in the size of edematous subchondral bone were noticed. Davatchi et al. performed single intra-articular BM-SCs injection in OA knees and described a marked clinical improvement in subjective parameters, although physical parameters improved much less. Kasemkijwattana et al. showed a good defect filling and repair of tissue with BM-SCs in patients with knee OA and a significant clinical improvement. Gigante et al. reported that BMSCs in patients with medial femoral condyle lesions, could result into normal arthroscopic appearance.

Nejadnik et al. compared the first-generation ACI technique with implantation of BM-SCs and showed a similar pattern of clinical and subjective improvement up to 2 years postoperatively. Haalem et al. used BM-SCs for treatment of articular knee cartilage defects and showed that symptoms improved after 12 months, and MRI revealed complete defect filling and complete surface congruity with cartilage tissue.

Centeno et al. showed encouraging results after treating a knee cartilage lesion by intra-articular injection of BM-SCs with an increase in cartilage and meniscus volume, and an improvement in range of motion and pain score. Wakitani et al. described results after the treatment of patello-femoral cartilage defects with BM-SCs and improvement in clinical symptoms at 6 months, which was maintained over 17–27 months. Adachi et al. in a large osteochondral knee defect treated with cultured BM-SCs noted a good cartilage and bone regeneration.

Wakitani et al. described the use of BM-SCs in knee OA reported clinical improvement by arthroscopic and histological scoring. They found clinical improvement in patients with full-thickness knee cartilage defects treated with BM-SCs after 6 months, which remained stable 5 years after treatment. Buda et al. showed good subchondral bone and cartilage tissue regeneration after arthroscopic implantation of BMSCs in osteochondral knee defects. Giannini et al. in patients with

OA found that one-step BMSC transplantation could lead to a good restoration of the cartilaginous layer.

Varma et al. reported an improvement in symptoms, with shortened hospital stay and better quality of life after BMSCs injection in patients with knee OA. Giannini et al. in treatment of osteochondral talar dome lesions with BMSCs showed newly formed tissue that were well integrated with the surrounding tissue with an improvement in clinical scores.

The immunomodulatory properties of AdSCs in patients with OA was previously shown which explain the healing effect of the cells in affected joint. These cells in knee cartilage defects were shown to improve pain and the quality-of-life. Kim et al. evaluated clinical and MRI outcomes after mesenchymal stem cell implantation in patients with knee osteoarthritis and showed encouraging clinical and MRI outcomes and repairing cartilage lesions in OA knees. Emadedin et al. in their long-term follow-up of intra-articular injection of autologous mesenchymal stem cells in patients with knee, ankle, or hip osteoarthritis revealed that in affected joints, they are safe and therapeutically beneficial. Davatchi et al. in their 5 years follow-up of mesenchymal stem cell therapy for knee osteoarthritis reported that transplant knees were all in a rather advanced stage of OA. Earlier transplantation may give better results in long-term follow-up.

Similar to above-mentioned studies, in our patient with severe knee OA and one year follow up after cell transplantation, the findings were satisfactory. The functional status of the knee, the number of stairs they could climb, the pain on visual analog scale and walking distance improved in our patient two months post-injection. Magnetic resonance images (MRI) at baseline, and post-stem cell injection revealed an extension of the repair tissue over subchondral bone. So as MSC transplantation is a simple technique, resulted into pain relief, minimized donor-site morbidity, provided a better quality of life, significantly improved cartilage quality with no need to hospitalization or surgery, cell transplantation can be considered as a reliable alternative treatment for chronic knee OA. These findings can be added to the literature on using MSCs for treatment of OA while we have compared our results completely with previous available studies chronologically.

References

1. Heidari B. Knee osteoarthritis prevalence, risk factors, pathogenesis and features: Part I. *Caspian J Intern Med.* 2011 Spring;2(2):205-12. PMID: 24024017; PMCID: PMC3766936.
2. Giorgino R, Albano D, Fusco S, Peretti GM, Mangiavini L, Messina C. Knee Osteoarthritis: Epidemiology, Pathogenesis, and Mesenchymal Stem Cells: What Else Is New? An Update. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023 Mar 29;24(7):6405. doi: 10.3390/ijms24076405. PMID: 37047377; PMCID: PMC10094836.
3. GBD 2019: Global burden of 369 diseases and injuries in 204 countries and territories, 1990–2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. Long H, Liu Q, Yin H, Diao N, Zhang Y, Lin J et al. Prevalence

trends of site-specific osteoarthritis from 1990 to 2019: Findings from the global burden of disease study 2019. *Arthritis Rheumatol* 2022; 74(7): 1172-1183.

4. Cieza A, Causey K, Kamenow K, Wulf Hansen S, Chatterji S, Vos T. Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease study 2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet*. 2020 Dec 19; 396(10267): 2006–2017
5. .Mehrabani D, Mojtahed Jaber F, Zakerinia M, Hadianfard MJ, Jalli R, Tanideh N, Zare S. The Healing Effect of Bone Marrow-Derived Stem Cells in Knee Osteoarthritis: A Case Report. *World J Plast Surg*. 2016 May;5(2):168-74. PMID: 27579273; PMCID: PMC5003953.